

Towards a faster Bitcoin network

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Transaction validation in the Bitcoin system is far from trivial due to the fact that transaction verification process is achieved in a distributed manner. Consequently, inconsistency in the replicas of the ledger that every node keeps are unavoidable. This results in a situation where uncertainty about the validity of a given transaction is introduced. Furthermore, a desynchronized replicas of ledger incentives attackers to impose their own transaction history, possibly using the same bitcoins more than once. However, the latency communication between nodes in the Bitcoin network is critical even though the probability of reaching an agreement about transaction history is high. The main motivation for this talk is to show how to overcome the problem of achieving agreement on a common transactions log among nodes in the Bitcoin network through maintaining faster information propagation in the network.

2. Aim

To speed up information propagation in the Bitcoin network, and presenting an entire network architecture that is based on the proximity of connectivity.

3. Material and methods

Aiming at alleviating the propagation delay problem, our research introduces a proximity-aware extension to the current Bitcoin protocol, named Locality Based Clustering (LBC), Ping Time Based Clustering (BCBPT), and Super Node Based Clustering (BCBSN). The ultimate purpose of the proposed protocols, that are based on how the clusters are formulated and the nodes define their membership, is to improve the information propagation delay in the Bitcoin network.

4. Results

We show, through simulations, that the proposed protocols define better clustering structures that optimize the performance of the transaction propagation delay over the Bitcoin protocol. However, BCBPT is more effective at

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reducing the transaction propagation delay compared to the LBC and BCBSN. The resistance of the Bitcoin network and the proposed protocols against the partitioning attack was evaluated. Evaluation results reveal that even though the Bitcoin network is more resistant against attackers than the proposed protocols, more resources need to be spent to split the network in the proposed protocols especially with a higher number of nodes.

5. Conclusions

We discovered that the providing less latency and geographical distance threshold would improve the transaction propagation delay with high proportion.

6. Keywords

Information propagation · Clustering · Bitcoin Network. Double spending attack

Author biography

Muntadher Fadhil Sallal Muntadher Sallal is a PhD research student at the age of 28 years at University of Portsmouth, UK. He is a Fellow lecturer at school of computing University. He has published more than 8 papers in reputed journals and conferences, and has been serving as an editorial board member of repute.